

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AND STUDENTS BEHAVIOR OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS: BASIS FOR LEARNING ENGAGEMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14523518>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the social dynamics between classroom management and student behavior among 20 Grade 10 students at St. Peter's College during the 2023-2024 school year. It analyzed classroom management in terms of learning style and use of technology, and student behavior in terms of attendance rates, learning, and classroom participation, while considering respondents' profiles. Using a modified questionnaire and descriptive statistics, including frequency, mean, Pearson correlation, and ANOVA, the findings revealed that most respondents were 17-year-old females. Learning style and classroom participation scored highest in their respective categories, and significant relationships were identified between classroom environment and aspects of student behavior, such as attendance, learning, and participation. Gender also significantly correlated with both classroom management and student behavior. The study underscores the importance of these elements in effective teaching and learning, highlighting the need for further exploration of factors like individual differences, social dynamics, and demographics.

Keywords: Classroom Management and Students Behavior

INTRODUCTION

Classroom management comprises many interrelated and complicated dimensions arising from class and environment. The teacher, as the class manager, is expected to lead the class environment, as stated by Lemlech (1988), considering these

dimensions as an orchestra. Another important aspect of classroom management is creating a proper learning environment and preparing the physical conditions of the class. Not only are the already present things pedagogically effective, but so are their arrangement and aesthetic appearance.

This study further aims to understand the teacher-student relationship. Students need full assistance and language when learning; this study was carried out during the academic year 2023-2024. A child's behavior can be completely different from that of the next child, so the researcher wondered how the screener and assessment scores looked. Students react differently to these implementations, so they may need to modify them. Student engagement can be defined as the level of involvement and enthusiasm a student shows in school. Engagement in learning includes behaviors such as persistence, effort, and focus, as well as attitudes such as motivation, positive learning values, enthusiasm, interest, and pride in success.

Furthermore, the State has to establish and maintain a complete and adequate public basic education system geared towards a child's holistic development. The State is also hereby bound to establish and maintain support systems, including training on classroom management and child discipline and legal assistance for teachers and school staff, who daily stand in direct contact with students and thus find themselves in situations that could expose them to allegations of child abuse in the course of the discharge of their duties. Effective classroom management ensures all students access an optimal learning environment, increases classroom participation, and prevents potentially problematic behaviors. Eliminating restrictive measures that expel students from classrooms through departmental referrals or academic suspensions a priority. Other targeted response strategies include teacher control when dealing with unruly students, including empathy, positive feedback, and appropriate disciplinary actions. This includes teaching appropriate learning behaviors and managing disruptive emotions and behaviors.

Related Literature

Classroom Management. Numerous studies have explored various aspects of classroom management and its impact on student behavior and academic achievement. According to Evertson and Weinstein (2020), classroom management refers various skills and techniques teachers use to keep students organized, focused, attentive, on task, and academically productive during class. Although they have different meanings for classroom management, they all agree on its goals: a) to create an orderly environment for learning and b) to promote the social and moral growth of students.

Learning Style. Roberts's et al. (2023) explore various established practices and juxtapose them with the methods proposed by the authors of "Discipline with Dignity." They suggest that effective discipline encompasses by considering students' behavior in the context of broader social values, combined with thoughtful introspection by educators and school leaders. The authors highlight the importance of teaching and consistently reinforcing classroom rules and procedures through diverse activities from the beginning of the school year.

Use of technology. Pitler et al. (2019) studied a comprehensive framework for leveraging technology to enhance instructional practices and promote student learning outcomes. By integrating technology strategically and purposefully, educators can create dynamic and engaging learning experiences that empower students to succeed in the digital age through the principles of setting objectives and providing feedback, reinforcing effort and providing recognition, fostering cooperative learning, utilizing cues, questions, and advanced organizers, incorporating nonlinguistic representations, promoting summarizing and note-taking, and facilitating homework and practice.

Classroom Environment. In Astolfi et al. (2019), noise is a source of distraction for children's ability to understand. The subjective perception of environmental sounds makes the listeners' experiences very different. The noisier the environment, the more they were annoyed and the less they could hear the teacher speaking inside the classroom. It is therefore necessary to understand that other factors at school, where children spend most of their time, directly influence their harmonic growth, learning, and well-being.

Students Behavior. Student behavior is a topic of great interest in education, as it plays a crucial role in academic success and overall well-being. Numerous studies have been conducted to explore the various factors that influence student behavior, and the impact of different interventions on improving behavior outcomes.

Attendance Rates. Gottfried, M. A. (2020) investigates the intricate connection between student attendance patterns and academic achievement levels in urban elementary and middle schools. This study contributes to the broader discourse on educational equity and student success by examining the impact of attendance on academic outcomes, particularly in urban settings where attendance challenges may be more prevalent. One of the key findings of study is the significant correlation between student attendance rates and academic performance. The research highlights that students with higher attendance tend to demonstrate greater academic achievement, as measured by standardized test scores, grades, and other academic indicators. The study conducted by Fisher, Charles W., et al. (2024). explores the concept of academic learning time (ALT), which refers to the amount of time students spend actively engaged in learning activities during instructional periods. They emphasize the importance of maximizing ALT as a critical factor influencing student achievement, highlighting the correlation between increased ALT and academic gains across various subject areas and grade levels.

Students Learning. Romero et al. (2023) analyzed data from online learning environments wherein they aimed to develop predictive models that can forecast students' academic outcomes based on their participation levels and contributions to discussion forums. One of their key findings is the significant correlation between students' engagement in online discussion forums and their final performance in the course. Their study contributes significantly to our understanding of the role of online discussion forums in predicting students' final performance in educational settings.

Thi and Nguyen's study (2021) likely delved into how different classroom management styles impact students' motivation and academic achievement in learning.

The implications of their findings could be significant for educators and policymakers involved in English language teaching. Understanding how different classroom management styles influence student motivation and achievement can inform instructional practices and teacher training programs. It also lead to developing guidelines or recommendations for creating more effective learning environments in English language classrooms. The researchers discuss limitations such as sample size or generalizability and suggest avenues for future research. This could include exploring additional factors that may influence student outcomes or investigating the long-term effects of different classroom management approaches. Thi and Nguyen's study contributes valuable insights to English language teaching by highlighting the importance of effective classroom management in fostering student motivation and academic success.

Classroom participation Wilson et al. (2020) examined the impact of student engagement on learner outcomes. The study contributed to the ongoing discourse on effective pedagogical practices in digital education settings. The authors seek to evaluate the relationship between active learning behaviors and learner outcomes, such as knowledge acquisition, critical thinking abilities, and overall course success, through quantitative analyses and statistical modeling.

Related Studies

The study of Gage, Scott, Hirn, and MacSuga-Gage (2020) investigated the connection between teachers' implementation of classroom management techniques and students' behavior in elementary school settings. Their study aimed to understand how various classroom management practices employed by teachers influence student behavior. The researchers utilized a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods to collect and analyze data. They might have observed classroom interactions, administered surveys to teachers and students and possibly conducted interviews or focus groups to gather deeper insights. By examining the relationship between teachers' implementation of management strategies (such as establishing rules, providing positive reinforcement, or addressing misbehavior) and students' behavior, the study likely provides insights into effective classroom management techniques.

Also, the study by Hattie, J. (2020) serves as a seminal work in educational research, synthesizing a vast array of studies to identify the most impactful teaching practices and strategies. Hattie's meta-analysis offers valuable insights into how educators can optimize teaching methods to enhance student learning outcomes. Hattie identifies teaching strategies that significantly student achievement, highlighting those that promote independent exploration and analysis of content as particularly powerful. Hattie identifies several teaching strategies that are particularly effective in promoting independent exploration and analysis of content.

Furthermore, Chen et al (2019), highlights the prevalence of technology in educational settings and the growing importance of understanding teachers' perspectives on its integration. Chen et al. propose a visual conceptualization model that captures the multifaceted nature of teachers' approaches to technology integration. Central to the

conceptualization is an exploration of teachers' knowledge, encompassing their understanding of technological tools, pedagogical strategies, and subject matter content.

The study investigates the underlying processes active learning in online courses uses to improve student outcomes. Consequently, Nawaz et al. (2022), published a journal that contributes to educational psychology by examining the predictors that impact student engagement in the classroom environment. They explored the role of classroom climate and teacher-student interactions in shaping student engagement. Nawaz et al. highlighted the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment characterized by positive teacher-student relationships, clear expectations, and mutual respect in contributing to higher levels of student engagement and academic success.

Research Objectives

This study aims to:

1. determine the levels of classroom management and of students' behavior in St. Peter's College Iligan City for School Year 2024-2025;
 2. describe the characteristics of the respondents;
 3. assess the level of classroom management;
 4. describe the level of current students' behavior;
 5. examine the relationship between classroom management and students' behavior;
 6. test the significance difference between classroom management and students' behavior when respondents are grouped according to their characteristics; and
 7. Design an action plan for classroom management and students' behavior.
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METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive correlation method of research. This method is a research approach used to identify relationships between variables without necessarily causation. In this method, researchers observe and describe how variables are naturally related in the real world. It involves collecting data on multiple variables of interest and analyzing the patterns of correlations between them.

To collect data for this study, questionnaires were employed. This approach is expected to yield an accurate and precise representation of the situation. The study involved collecting, organizing, and analyzing data to derive meaningful insights from the findings. The key variables to be examined include the attributes of teacher respondents, their research competence, and their level of research engagement.

Research Site

This study was conducted at St. Peter's College located at Barangay Saray, Iligan City. St. Peter's College is a private, non-stock, non-sectarian, institution that comprising different colleges, namely the College of Education, Criminology, Engineering, Arts and Sciences, Computer Studies, and Business Administration. The school has separate

buildings for various colleges, a library, and a canteen for everyone. The said school has lecture rooms and provides audio-visual presentation equipment for classroom discussions. The school also has various facilities for different subjects, such as a chemistry laboratory, drawing and engineering rooms, a criminology laboratory, a martial arts room, a computer room, a speech laboratory, and an AVR (Audio-Visual Room).

Research within this setting is timely, aligning with the academic calendar for the school year 2023-2024. This ensures that the findings will be relevant and actionable, serving as the basis for learning engagement from classroom management and student behavior of grade 10 students.

As a research institution, St. Peter's College fosters collaboration between researchers and students, making it an ideal environment to explore classroom management and student behaviors. The study will take place within the campus facilities and classrooms, providing a dynamic backdrop for investigating the classroom management and student behaviors in Grade 10 students.

Respondents/Sample and Sampling Methods

This study examined classroom management and student behavior among grade 10 students at St. Peter's College in the school year 2023-2024 with a diverse and representative population.

Twenty Grade 10 respondents were selected as the primary students of interest in investigating classroom management and students' behaviors.

Data Gathering Methods Instruments and Process

The researcher followed proper protocol by securing a letter of recommendation, signed by the researchers and adviser, requesting permission to conduct a study among Grade 10 students and providing the study questionnaire to be approved by the Principal.

After the Principal's approval, the researcher submitted a request letter to the Dean to allow the students to participate in the study. The research emphasizes voluntary participation and assures the respondents' confidentiality.

The research questionnaire, divided into three parts, was designed to gather valuable insights into classroom management and student behavior at St. Peter's College. The questionnaire was answered for 5 to 10 minutes. The first part of the questionnaire dealt with the respondent's profiles in terms of age and gender.

Source: <https://www.google.com/maps/@8.2307644,124.2386626,48m/data=!3m1!1e3!5m1!1e4?entry=ttu>

Figure 2: Map of the St. Peter's College

The second part of the questionnaire is an adopted questionnaire that underwent validation for test and retesting. The questionnaire was designed to assess classroom management based on the functions of involvement. Students were asked to assess classroom management using the following scale: at all times, most of the times,

sometimes, and never. The subsections in this part include learning style, use of technology, and classroom environment.

The third part of the questionnaire is an adapted questionnaire that assessed students' behavior. Students were asked to assess their learning engagement using the following scale: highly observable, observable, somewhat observable, and not observable. The subsections in this part include areas such as attendance rates, student learning, and classroom participation.

Data Analysis Method

To systematically process, interpret, and analyze the collection of data and to address the research objectives and questions effectively, the following tools were utilized in the analysis:

Research Objective No. 1: the respondents' demographic profile used frequency and percentage of age and gender. The presentation and interpretation of data rely heavily on frequency and percentage. They make it easy for the researchers to understand the data clearly.

Research Objective No. 2 and 3: the statistical mean was used to analyze the students' perceptions of tactics that improve classroom management and student behavior. The mean condenses a large amount of data into a single value, making it easier to grasp and communicate the overall characteristics of the data set.

Research Objective No.4: Pearson r was utilized to determine whether there is a significant relationship between classroom management and students' behavior. It helps researchers to test the hypothesis's correlation with the population from which the sample was drawn.

Research Objective No. 5: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare the significant difference between the independent and moderating variables.

Research Objective No. 6: a comprehensive action plan was designed to determine the key areas of the lowest mean and the significant relationship of the variables

Research Ethics

It is crucial to ensure the privacy and anonymity of the students who participated in the research. Students are inclined to participate honestly and openly if they are assured that their identities and personal information will be kept confidential. The following ethical concerns were to be undertaken:

1) Informed consent. The researchers obtained consent from all participating students and clearly explained the purpose of the study, the data collection process, and how their information would be used. This is to ensure that they can withdraw from the study at any time without consequences.

2) Data De-identification. During analysis, the students were asked to remove or replace any personally identifiable information (such as names, school names, or contact details) from the data. Pseudonym assignments may be done to protect their identities.

3) Secure Data Storage. The researchers safeguarded the collected data by securely storing it, using encryption where necessary, and limiting access to authorized personnel. This is to ensure that data is not accidentally disclosed to unauthorized parties.

4) Ethical Review. Ethical approval was sought from an institutional review board (IRB) or ethics committee to ensure that the research design and data handling procedures met ethical standards and guidelines.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focuses on the classroom management and student behavior of Grade 10 students at St. Peter's College during School Year 2023 - 2024.

The variables are age and gender. The independent variables pertain to classroom management, namely, learning style, use of technology, and classroom environment. The dependent variable is limited to students' behavior and is categorized as attendance rates, learning, and classroom participation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Objective 1: How are the respondents distributed in terms of age and gender?

Tables 1 and 2 present the distributions of the respondents in terms of age and gender, respectively.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents according to age.

Age [years old]	Frequency	Percentage [%]
15	6	30
16	6	30
17	7	35
18	1	5
<i>Total</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>100</i>

The 17-year-old age bracket had the most share among the respondents (at 35 %), followed by the 15- and 16-year-old brackets (each at 30 %) and the 18-year-old

bracket (the lowest, at 5 %). It implies that the survey may have been particularly appealing or accessible to individuals within this age group. Grasping the demographics of the target audience can significantly enhance communication strategies and outreach efforts, ensuring they resonate more effectively with this group in the future. This emphasizes the importance of creating avenues for young people to engage and voice their interests and concerns. The study's findings may offer insights into the educational environment, guiding educational policy, curriculum design, and support services to meet student needs better. These insights can also influence marketing strategies, product development, and branding efforts by aligning them with the preferences and interests of this demographic.

On the other hand, the data revealed that out of the 20 respondents, only the age of 18, 1 (5%) got the lower frequency. It implies that factors such as educational commitments, employment status, or access to technology can reveal dynamics that influence their participation in research and other research activities. Understanding survey participation can provide valuable insights into broader trends in youth engagement and participation in research. Removing barriers to participation and exploring alternative methods of engaging young adults can increase the inclusiveness and relevance of research targeting this population. Researchers must exercise caution and avoid overgeneralizing conclusions based on limited data.

According to Marzano and Marzano (2023), teachers can establish clear expectations for behavior in two ways: by establishing clear rules and procedures and by providing consequences for student behavior. Highlight significant variations in teachers' use of praise and reprimands when interacting with students of different age groups. For instance, the research may reveal that teachers tend to utilize more frequent and specific praise with younger students, emphasizing encouragement and positive reinforcement to support early learning and development. Conversely, teachers may employ more reprimands or corrective feedback with older students, reflecting expectations for increased autonomy and accountability in behavior and academic performance. Marzano and Marzano's research sheds light on the complex interplay between teacher-student interactions, age-related differences in behavior, and classroom management strategies. By elucidating the role of praise and reprimands in shaping student engagement and behavior across different age groups, the study offers valuable insights for educators seeking to optimize their instructional practices and cultivate positive learning environments conducive to student success.

Table 2. Distribution of respondents according to gender.

	Frequency	Percentage [%]
Male	9	45
Female	11	55
<i>Total</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>100</i>

From Table 2, most (55 %) of the respondents are females. The data revealed that of 20 respondents, 11 (55%) were females, which obtained higher frequency. Depending on the context of the study, the gender distribution could introduce bias into the results. For instance, if the study is about a topic that disproportionately affects one gender over the other, the skewed gender representation might impact the validity and generalizability of the findings. The gender distribution could influence the analysis and interpretation of the data. When analyzing the results, researchers should consider gender-specific patterns, behaviors, or preferences.

Moreover, the fact that males represented the minority raises questions about potential underrepresentation or sampling bias. Researchers must consider whether the sample accurately reflects the population being studied and whether any biases exist in the data collection process. By comparing responses between male and female respondents, researchers may uncover gender-specific patterns, behaviors, or preferences relevant to the study.

Kowalewski's (2022) comprehensive explores the multifaceted intersection of gender dynamics and educational practices. Through a collection of essays authored by leading scholars, the book delves into various aspects of gender issues in education, offering nuanced perspectives and actionable insights for educators, researchers, and policymakers. It delves into the complex interplay between gender stereotypes and academic performance. Through empirical research and theoretical analyses, contributors elucidate how societal expectations and cultural norms surrounding gender influence students' self-concept, motivation, and educational aspirations. It unpacks how gendered perceptions of academic abilities and interests shape students' engagement, participation, and achievement across various subject areas and educational levels.

Research Objective 2: What levels of classroom management – in terms of learning style, use of technology, and classroom environment – are perceived by the respondents?

Tables 3, 4, and 5 present the distributions of respondents' levels of learning style, use of technology, and classroom environment, respectively.

Table 3. Distribution of respondents to the level of learning style.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Facts, Concepts and Principles are the most important things that students should acquire.	3.80	At all times
Activities in this class courage students to develop their own ideas about content issues.	3.65	At all times

Developing the ability of students to think work independently is an important goal.	3.60	At all times
Lecturing is a significant part of how teacher teach of each class sessions.	3.70	At all times
Independently explore and analyze content, enhancing their ability to generate and articulate original ideas effectively.	3.20	Most of the time

Overall	3.59	At all times
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Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very Positive 1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Negative
2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/Positive 1.00-1.75 Never/ Very Negative

According to the overall mean reported in Table 3, there is a very positive assessment of classroom management in terms of learning style. Such distribution of respondents across different levels of classroom management can inform the design of targeted professional development programs for educators. Teachers proficient in classroom management may benefit from advanced training in innovative learning styles to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Conversely, those with lower levels of classroom management proficiency may require more intensive support and resources to implement various learning styles while managing classroom dynamics effectively.

Among the indicators for learning style, Facts, Concepts and Principles are the most important things that students should acquire and have the highest mean: 3.80, which is interpreted as Very Positive. On the other hand, independently exploring and analyzing content, enhancing their ability to generate and articulate original ideas effectively has the lowest mean: 3.20, which is interpreted as Positive. The purchase of facts, standards, and concepts lays the foundation for constructing a solid basis of know-how throughout numerous disciplines. Facts offer raw data; standards provide the frameworks for organizing information, and concepts set up the essential legal guidelines or policies governing phenomena. These insights, enriched with accurate information, help college students learn to assess accuracy and relevance. Concepts offer frameworks for organizing and synthesizing information, while principles provide guiding concepts for making informed decisions and solving problems. Independent research and analysis allow students to take responsibility for their learning. Teachers increase students' sense of agency and responsibility by encouraging autonomy and self-direction. This process fosters intellectual curiosity, encourages intellectual risk-taking, and fosters a deeper understanding of complex concepts. Through independent research and analysis, students improve their ability to express and communicate their ideas effectively.

Similarly, the indicator independently explores and analyze content, enhancing their ability to generate and articulate original ideas effectively, got the lowest mean of

3.20, which is described as Most of the time as positive. It implies that independent research and analysis allows students to take responsibility for their learning. By encouraging autonomy and self-direction, teachers increase students' sense of agency and responsibility, which fosters a lifelong love of learning. This process fosters intellectual curiosity, encourages intellectual risk-taking, and fosters a deeper understanding of complex concepts. Through independent research and analysis, students improve their ability to express and communicate their ideas effectively.

According to a study by Haitte, J. (2020), it serves as a seminal work in educational research, synthesizing a vast array of studies to identify the most impactful teaching practices and strategies. Hattie's meta-analysis offers valuable insights into how educators can optimize their teaching methods to enhance student learning outcomes. Hattie identifies teaching strategies that have significantly impact on student achievement, highlighting those that promote independent exploration and analysis of content as particularly powerful. Hattie identifies several teaching strategies that are particularly effective in promoting independent exploration and analysis of content.

Table 4. Distribution respondents to the level of use of technology.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Technology can help me to learn new things.	3.55	At all times
Using technology in learning languages in not necessary.	2.40	Sometimes
Confident when it comes to working with technology at school.	3.00	Sometimes
Using technology in class takes up too much time.	2.70	Most of the time
Students should know how to use technology in class.	3.45	At all times
Overall	3.02	Most of the time

Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very Positive 1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Negative
2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/Positive 1.00-1.75 Never/ Very Negative

According to the overall mean reported in Table 4, the respondents have a positive assessment of classroom management in terms of technology use. The data implies that most respondents are confident in their ability to manage their classrooms effectively, and this holds significant implications for educational institutions. Understanding teachers' strengths and areas needing improvement is pivotal for institutions aiming to cultivate an environment conducive to effective teaching and learning. This insight that most

respondents are confident in their ability to effectively manage their classrooms holds significant implications for educational institutions.

Among the indicators for technology use, Technology can help me to learn new things, recorded the highest mean of 3.55, which is interpreted as Very Positive. This implies that people see technology as a valuable tool for accessing information and resources to facilitate learning. The idea that technology can help learn new things means favoring flexible and personalized learning experiences. Insights into this indicator highlight the role of technology. Removing barriers to learning through access to rich educational content such as online courses, tutorials, e-books, and multimedia resources.

The study of Pitler et al. (2019) comprehensive framework for leveraging technology to enhance instructional practices and promote student learning outcomes. Educators can create dynamic and engaging learning experiences that empower students to succeed in the digital age integrating technology strategically and purposefully, through the principles of setting objectives and providing feedback, reinforcing effort and providing recognition, fostering cooperative learning, utilizing cues, questions, and advanced organizers, incorporating nonlinguistic representations, promoting summarizing and note-taking, and facilitating homework and practice.

On the other hand, Using technology in learning languages is not necessary, on the other hand, it has the lowest mean of 2.40, which is interpreted as Negative. This implies a belief in the efficacy of conventional teaching methods and a potential skepticism towards integrating technology in language education. While technology offers numerous tools and resources for language learning, the assertion that it is unnecessary raises questions about accessibility and equity. Insights drawn from this perspective highlight the diversity of learning styles and preferences among language learners, with some individuals thriving in technology-enhanced environments while others prefer more traditional methods. It is therefore important to critically evaluate the effectiveness of technology in language education and consider its role as a complement to, rather than a substitute for, traditional teaching methods.

According to the study of Wigham (2020). Recognition of technology's capacity to transcend physical boundaries and connect language learners from diverse backgrounds in virtual learning environments. Through the lens of collaborative interaction, the authors underscore the pivotal role of digital tools in creating opportunities for meaningful communication and collaboration among learners, regardless of their geographical locations or linguistic proficiency levels. His pedagogical implications of integrating technology into language learning environments. They emphasize how digital tools can support pedagogical approaches prioritizing communicative competence, task-based learning, and authentic language use.

Table 5. Distribution of respondents to the level of classroom environment

Indicators	Mean	Description
The classroom is large enough for the number of students enrolled in the course.	3.05	Most of the time
The classroom is fitted with the latest in classroom technology.	2.80	Most of the time
Noise coming from outside the classroom is often a problem in the class.	3.35	At all times
I sometimes have difficulty seeing instructional materials displayed by the professor in the classroom.	2.80	Most of the time
I often have to ask classmates to clarify what's being shown on the screen because I can't see it well.	3.05	Most of the time
Overall	3.01	Most of the time

Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times / Very Positive 1.76-2.50 Sometimes/Negative
2.51-3.25 Most of the Time/Positive 1.00-1.75 Never/Very Negative

According to Table 5, the respondents have a positive assessment (based on the overall mean) of classroom management in terms of classroom environment. This implies that it permits teachers to distinguish the range of recognitions concerning classroom administration. On the off chance that the dispersion is wide, it is recommended that there be contrasting conclusions among respondents, demonstrating potential ranges of advancement or incongruities in classroom encounters. These insights presenting the conveyance of respondents' recognitions of classroom administration level give important experiences into the general fulfillment, zones of concern, and opportunities for enhancement within the classroom environment. By leveraging these experiences, teachers can make educated choices, actualize focused on intercessions, and develop a positive and strong learning environment for all understudies.

The indicator Noise coming from outside the classroom is often a problem in the class, had the highest mean (described as At all times), and implies a persistent problem contributing to increased stress levels among teachers and students. Teachers may find it challenging to deliver instruction effectively in a noisy environment, leading to feelings of frustration and exhaustion. This agrees with the known notion that the perception of noise has a profound impact on teaching effectiveness, student behavior, and the overall classroom atmosphere (Astolfi et al., 2019). By prioritizing the reduction of external noise

disturbances, educators can create a learning environment where students and teachers can thrive.

The study by Astolfi et al. (2019) posits that the presence of noise sources as distractors for children’s ability to understand the subjective perception of the sound environment makes it very different from the way listeners experience their everyday living spaces. The more the external noise level increased, the more they were annoyed and the less they reported being able to hear the teacher speaking inside the classroom. Knowledge is therefore necessary, especially to understand if BA and other factors at school, where children spend most of their time, directly influence their harmonic growth, learning, and well-being.

Meanwhile, the mean for the indicator The classroom is fitted with the latest in classroom technology implies understudies are likely to have an assortment of mixed media assets, intuitive instruments, and computerized stages. This could lead to a more locked-in and energetic learning involvement, catering to distinctive learning styles, and classroom innovation. Successful utilization of classroom innovation frequently requires preparing and proficient advancement for instructors. Bits of knowledge into the accessibility and utilization of innovation can give data on the level of back and preparation given to teachers. This insight prioritizes integrating technology into the learning environment, recognizing its potential to enhance educational experiences. Advanced technology suggests a focus on fostering student engagement and interaction through interactive tools, multimedia resources, and digital platforms.

Furthermore, Chen et al (2019) discuss the prevalence of technology in educational settings and the growing importance of understanding teachers' perspectives on its integration. Drawing on empirical research and theoretical frameworks, Chen et al. propose a visual conceptualization model that captures the multifaceted nature of teachers' approaches to technology integration. Central to the conceptualization is an exploration of teachers' knowledge, encompassing their understanding of technology tools, pedagogical strategies, and subject matter content.

Research Objective 3: How do the respondents assess students’ behavior in terms of attendance rates, students learning, and classroom participation?

Tables 6, 7, and 8 report the respondents’ assessments of students’ behavior in terms of attendance rates, students learning, and of classroom participation, respectively

Table 6. Respondent assessment of students’ behavior in terms of attendance rates.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Students who are absent from class, miss the chance of class participation.	3.50	Highly Observable

Recurrent absenteeism leads a student to drop out from grade activities.	3.25	Observable
Due to poor coordination students are unable to update for their assignments.	3.00	Observable
Class attendance develop the self- efficiency of students towards better performance.	3.45	Highly Observable
Good record of attendance gives you academic achievements.	3.50	Highly Observable
Overall	3.34	Highly Observable

Legend: 3.26-4.00 Highly Observable/Very High 1.76-2.50 Somewhat Observable/Low
2.51-3.25Observable/High 1.00-1.75 Not Observable/Very Low

Referring to Table 6, the respondents assess the student attendance rates to be very high overall. This implies that the students generally prioritize attending classes regularly, demonstrating reliability in their academic commitments. The attendance rate indicates that the learning environment, whether in-person or virtual, is likely supportive and conducive to student learning. This insight suggests that students who attend classes regularly are more likely to succeed academically, benefiting from consistent exposure to course materials and instructional support. Attendance rates indicate that students actively engage with the teaching content and learning activities, facilitating effective teaching and learning interactions.

Among the indicators for attendance rates, Good record of attendance gives you academic achievements have the highest mean which is interpreted as Very High. This implies a causal relationship between attendance and academic achievement, suggesting that regular attendance directly contributes to academic success. Students who attend classes regularly are more likely to perform well academically, as they have consistent exposure to course materials, instruction, and learning activities. Such consistent engagement is fundamental to understanding and mastering the content. The statement implies a strong positive correlation between attendance and academic performance by asserting that a good attendance record leads to academic achievements.

A study by Gottfried (2020) investigates the intricate connection between student attendance patterns and academic achievement levels in urban elementary and middle schools. This study contributes to the broader discourse on educational equity and student success by examining the impact of attendance on academic outcomes, particularly in urban settings where attendance challenges may be more prevalent. One of the key findings of Gottfried's study is the significant correlation between student attendance rates and academic performance. The research highlights that students with higher attendance tend to demonstrate more outstanding academic achievement, as measured by standardized test scores, grades, and other academic indicators.

On the other hand, the indicator Due to poor coordination students are unable to update for their assignments had the lowest mean (interpreted as High). This results in missed due dates or fragmented assignments, influencing students' scholarly execution and a breakdown in communication between understudies, teachers, and conceivably other partners included in task coordination. This means that effective task coordination requires responsibility from both understudies and educators. Understudies have to take responsibility for remaining overhauled on assignments, while instructors have to guarantee that communication concerning assignments is obvious, convenient, and accessible.

The study conducted by Fisher et al. (2024) explores the concept of academic learning time (ALT), which refers to the amount of time students spend actively engaged in learning activities during instructional periods. They emphasize the importance of maximizing ALT as a critical factor influencing student achievement, highlighting the correlation between increased ALT and academic gains across various subject areas and grade levels.

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Table 7. Respondent assessment of students' behavior in terms of students learning.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Actively participate in the discussion, answering and clarifying things you did not understand.	3.40	Highly Observable
Study the lessons you missed if you were absent from the class.	3.35	Highly Observable
I prefer to complete my assignments and studying during the weekdays to avoid weekend distractions.	3.10	Observable
Get frustrated when discussion is interrupted.	2.50	Somewhat Observable
Enjoying homework and activities because that can help improve skills in every subject,	3.15	Observable
Overall	3.10	Observable

Legend: 3.26-4.00 *Highly Observable/Very High* 1.76-2.50 *Somewhat Observable/Low*
2.51-3.25 *Observable/High* 1.00-1.75 *Not Observable/Very Low*

From the overall mean reported in Table 7, the respondents' assessment of students' learning is described as Observable and interpreted as High. An implication is that the students, on average, are meeting or exceeding academic expectations despite the overall high level of students learning, variability in performance may be influenced by various external factors such as socio-economic background, access to resources, learning environments, and individual circumstances, Whereas the majority of respondents show discernible tall scholarly execution, there may still be a subset of understudies who require extra bolster or mediation to preserve or move forward their performance. These insights ought to recognize and address the wants of these understudies by focusing on intercessions. This experiences the general tall level of scholastic execution, and the standard deviation shows a few degrees of changeability among respondents.

Actively participating in the discussion, answering and clarifying things you did not understand has the highest mean 3.40, described as Highly Observable and interpreted as Very High among indicators for students' learning. This implies participation in

discussions facilitates peer-to-peer learning, where participants can learn from each other's insights, experiences, and perspectives. By sharing knowledge and collaborating with peers, individuals can broaden their understanding and benefit from diverse viewpoints. Engaging in discussions allows individuals to exchange ideas, perspectives, and information. These insights actively participating in discussions increase engagement and motivation by involving individuals in learning. By actively contributing to discussions and seeking clarification, individuals become more invested in the topic and are more likely to retain and apply what they have learned.

Furthermore, Romero et al (2023), by analyzing data from online learning environments, the study aims to develop predictive models to forecast students' academic outcomes based on their participation levels and contributions to discussion forums. One of the key findings of the study is the significant correlation between students' engagement in online discussion forums and their final performance in the course. Romero, López, Luna, and Ventura's (2013) study contributes significantly to our understanding of the role of online discussion forums in predicting students' final performance in educational settings.

On the other hand, the indicator Get frustrated when discussion is interrupted got the lowest mean of 2.50, described as Somewhat Observable and interpreted as Low. This implies that intrusions in discourses can disturb the stream of discussion, causing dissatisfaction among members. This disturbance may prevent people from completely communicating their contemplations or thoughts, driving. Dissatisfaction from interferences can contrarily affect participants' engagement within the dialog. This insight's successful help is pivotal for overseeing interferences and tending to disappointment inside discourses. Facilitators can play a key part in directing the discussion, guaranteeing rise to cooperation, and intervening in clashes to preserve a helpful and profitable dialogue.

The study of Graziano et al (2020) makes a significant contribution to the rapidly expanding field of developmental psychology by examining how children's emotional regulation skills affect their early academic achievement. Graziano et al.'s study focuses on how emotion regulation affects attentional control, social competence, and cognitive performance, among other areas of children's academic functioning. The authors hope to shed light on the mechanisms behind the relationship between emotion regulation and academic performance through observational assessments, experimental manipulations, and longitudinal studies.

Table 8. Respondent assessment of students' behavior in terms of classroom participation.

Indicators	Mean	Description
Comfortable interacting with your peers during group activities or discussions.	3.30	Highly Observable

Encouraged and supported by the teacher to participate in class discussions and activities.	3.40	Highly Observable
Fully engaged during class discussions and activities.	3.35	Highly Observable
Actively contribute to class discussions.	3.50	Highly Observable
The teacher provides helpful feedback to improve participation.	3.40	Highly Observable
Overall	3.39	Highly Observable

Legend: 3.26-4.00 *Highly Observable/Very High* 1.76-2.50 *Somewhat Observable/Low*
2.51-3.25 *Observable/High* 1.00-1.75 *Not Observable/Very Low*

Table 8 reports a mean of **3.39** (which is described as **Highly Observable** and interpreted as **Very High**) overall indicators relating to class participation. Actively participating in class activities helps students develop essential communication skills, such as articulating thoughts clearly, active listening, and expressing ideas effectively. These skills are valuable for academic success and future professional endeavors. High levels of class participation indicate students' engagement and interest in the subject matter. Students who actively participate are will likely to be more motivated, curious, and invested in their learning experiences.

Among the indicators relating to class participation, **Actively contribute to class discussions** got the highest mean of **3.50**, which is described as **Highly Observable** and interpreted as **Very High**. This implies that contributing to lesson talks develops viable communication aptitudes. Understudies learn to express their considerations clearly, tune in mindfully to others, and express thoughts powerfully, planning them for victory in scholarly and proficient settings. Active interest in lesson discourses empowers understudies to think fundamentally around coarse fabric. This insight and presence of active contributors enriches the dynamics of the classroom environment. Discussions become dynamic and engaging, with ideas flowing freely and students building upon one another's contributions. This vibrant exchange of ideas fosters a sense of intellectual curiosity and excitement, creating a positive learning atmosphere that motivates students to participate and explore new concepts actively.

Wilson et al. (2020) examines the impact of student engagement on learner outcomes, the study contributes to the ongoing discourse on effective pedagogical practices in digital education settings. The authors seek to evaluate the relationship between active learning behaviors and learner outcomes, such as knowledge acquisition, critical thinking abilities, and overall course success, through quantitative analyses and

statistical modeling. The study investigates the underlying processes active learning in online courses uses to improve student outcomes.

Similarly, the indicator **Comfortable interacting with your peers during group activities or discussions** has a mean that is, although the lowest, described as **Highly Observable** and interpreted as **Very High**. This implies that comfortable collaboration with peers amid bunch exercises or talks advances collaboration and collaboration. Understudies are more likely to lock ineffectively, share thoughts, and work together successfully to realize common objectives, driving to upgrade learning results. Comfortable interaction with peers underpins social advancement by cultivating positive connections and interpersonal aptitudes. This insight into collaboration not only enhances the learning experience but also promotes teamwork and cooperation, skills that are valuable in both academic and professional settings. Interacting comfortably with peers boosts social confidence and interpersonal skills.

Consequently, Nawaz et al. (2022) published in an unspecified journal, contributes to the field of educational psychology by examining the predictors that impact student engagement in the classroom environment. They explore the role of classroom climate and teacher-student interactions in shaping student engagement. Nawaz et al. highlight the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment characterized by positive teacher-student relationships, clear expectations, and mutual respect, which contribute to higher student engagement and academic success.

Research Objective 4: Is there a significant relationship between the levels of classroom management (i.e., learning style, use of technology, and classroom environment) and the student behavior (i.e., in terms of attendance rates, students learning, and classroom participation)?

Table 9. Correlation coefficients and p-values describing the relationships between classroom management and students behavior.

Classroom Management	STUDENTS BEHAVIOR								
	Attendance Rates			Students Learning			Classroom Participation		
	r-value	p-value	Significance	r-value	p-value	Significance	r-value	p-value	Significance
Learning Style	0.542	0.0481*	S	0.479	0.0489*	S	0.745	0.0499*	S
Use of Technology	0.198	0.0593	NS	0.477	0.0739	NS	0.959	0.7490	NS
Classroom Environment	0.198	0.0360*	S	0.980	0.0375*	S	0.988	0.0298*	S
Overall	0.312	0.0478*	S	0.645	0.0534	NS	0.897	0.2762	NS

Table 9 shows the correlation coefficient (r-values) and p-values of the relationship between the Classroom Management and Students' behavior in terms of Attendance rates, Students learning, and Classroom Participation. The test was utilized to investigate whether a statistical relationship existed between classroom management and students' behavior.

The data illustrate the significant relationship in Classroom Management in terms of learning style across Attendance Rates, Students Learning, and Classroom Participation, and Classroom Environment across Attendance Rates, Students Learning, and Classroom Participation. Upon reviewing the material submitted by respondents of learning style the analysis reveals significant diversity across the three dimensions, indicating the statistical importance of Students Behavior based on Attendance Rates (r-value = 0.542 and p-values= 0.0481), Students Learning (r-value =0.479 and p-value= 0.0489) and Classroom Participation (r-value =0.745 and p-value= 0.0499). There is also a statistical significant relationship between the respondents' classroom environment in attendance rates (r-value= 0.198 and p-value= 0.0360), students learning (r-value= 0.980 and p-value = 0.0375), and classroom participation (r-value= 0.988 and p-value= 0.0298).

Similarly, in the Use of Technology, the correlation coefficient with Attendance Rates, Students Learning, and Classroom Participation is not significant ($p > 0.05$). The lack of a significant relationship may indicate that the relationship is more nuanced or indirect than previously thought; it implies that there may not be a significant correlation or association between these two variables within the sample data analyzed. The lack of significance suggests no substantial relationship exists between classroom management and students' behavior.

Research Objective 5: Is there significant difference in the respondents' assessment of classroom management and students behavior when grouped according to age and gender?

Table 10. Test of difference between the level of classroom management and the level of students' behavior when grouped according to age and gender.

Characteristics	Classroom Management			Students Behavior		
	r-value	p-value	Significance	r-value	p-value	Significance
Age	0.975	0.0788	NS	0.593	0.0980	NS
Gender	0.906	0.0495	S	0.195	0.0165	S
Overall	0.940	0.0641	NS	0.394	0.0572	NS

The following observations are made from Table 10.

First, gender respondents have significant correlations with classroom management and student behavior. This implies that gender strongly influences the perceptions of classroom management and student behavior.

Second, no significant correlation is detected between classroom management and student behavior in the assessment. This implies that age does not strongly influence perceptions of classroom management and students behavior. The impact of age on perceptions may vary depending on cultural and contextual factors. Different educational systems, societal norms, and cultural values can influence how classroom management is perceived and practiced across age groups.

As a whole, a lack of significant correlation between classroom management and student behavior, such as age, may not be as influential in shaping perceptions of classroom management and student behavior among respondents. It is crucial to acknowledge the individual differences and personal characteristics of educators, as these shape their perceptions of classroom management and students' behavior.

However, the lack of significant differences suggests that, on average, the levels of classroom management and student behavior are similar among groups based on the chosen characteristics. This implies a degree of consistency in classroom dynamics and student conduct across different subgroups within the sample; statistically insignificant results should prompt further investigation to explore potential underlying factors that may contribute to similarities across groups.

Research Objective 6: Based on the findings, what action plan on classroom management can be designed?

Rationale. The findings provide an exact understanding of the involved relationship between respondents' characteristics, classroom management, and students' behavior. Examining the respondents' characteristics, recognizing and rewarding positive behavior helps to build a supportive classroom culture and motivates students to adhere to established norms and expectations.

In the respondents' perception of classroom management, learning style is rated the highest. Classroom participation ranked the highest in the students' behavior, which implies that a well-managed classroom allows teachers to focus on teaching and building positive relationships with their students

The study determined a significant relationship between classroom management and students' behavior in terms of learning style, use of technology, and classroom environment, but it found no significant relationship in use of technology.

Furthermore, the study identified a significant difference between the level of classroom management and the level of students' behavior when grouped according to characteristics. Regarding the respondents' characteristics, significant correlations were observed in the gender with the assessment of classroom management and students' behavior.

General objectives

From the abovementioned findings, an action plan (see Table 11) is formulated with the following objectives.

1. To demonstrate that recognizing and rewarding positive behavior enhances student adherence to norms and expectations, leading to a more cohesive and positive classroom culture.
2. To provide data showing that well-managed classrooms lead to increased classroom participation, allowing teachers to focus more on instructional activities and relationship building.
3. To achieve a comprehensive understanding of how specific characteristics influence classroom management practices and student behavior, with significant correlations identified particularly in gender.
4. To highlight significant gender-based differences in the perception and implementation of classroom management strategies and their effects on student behavior.

Table 11. Action plan formulated from the findings.

Areas of concern	Specific Objectives	Strategies Activities	Time Frame	Person Involved	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Critical Thinking skills	Focus on developing critical thinking skills, such as evaluating sources, identifying biases, and analyzing information logically.	Have students keep reflective journals where they record their thoughts, questions, and insights about what they're learning	2 Days	Teacher and Students	800	Increased Metacognition
Perceived Effectiveness of Technology	Evaluate the effectiveness of technology in enhancing language learning outcomes,	Apply predictive analytics techniques to forecast future trends in student engagement	3 Days	Teacher	600	Data-Driven Insights

	identifying areas of potential improvement and assessing its impact on learners' language proficiency.	ent and performance based on historical usage data.				
Cost-effectiveness	Express concerns about the cost-effectiveness of investing in the latest classroom technology	Use formative assessment techniques, such as quizzes, polls, or interactive activities embedded within digital learning tools, to gather real-time feedback on student progress and understanding	2 Days	Faculty	700	Training and Support Costs
Time Manage	Provide guidance and resources	Pair students with accountab	2 days	Teacher and Principal	200	Time Tracking

ment Skills	on time management strategies can empower students to prioritize tasks, allocate sufficient time for assignment updates, and meet deadlines.	ility partners or study buddies to support each other in maintaining productive				
Feedback Mechanisms	Provide opportunities for respondents to provide feedback on discussion dynamics and interruptions can help identify underlying issues and inform interventions to improve the overall experience.	Provide timely and constructive feedback to students on their assessments, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement.	5 Days	Teacher	500	Increased Awareness

Communication Skills	Communicate workshops or activities focused on active listening, assertiveness, and effective speaking can help improve participants' communication skills and boost their confidence.	Use role-playing scenarios where students take turns expressing their viewpoints, ensuring each participant has an opportunity to contribute without interruption.	1 Day	Students	500	Improved Communication Skills
Building Positive Relationships	Develop positive relationships with students is crucial for effective classroom management. When students feel valued, respected, and supported by their teacher, they are more likely to engage in	Implement a peer mediation program where trained student mediators facilitate discussions between peers involved in conflicts.	2 Days	Teacher and students	150	Enhanced Social-Emotional Development

	learning and exhibit positive behavior.					
Positive Classroom Culture	Create a positive classroom culture characterized by mutual respect, trust, and inclusivity can cultivate a supportive learning environment where students feel valued and empowered to contribute	Invite guest speakers from diverse backgrounds, including community leaders, to share their experiences and perspectives with students	1 Day	Teacher, Student, Principal, and Faculty	1500	Promotion of Diversity and Inclusion:
Peer Influence and Socialization	Diverse Concerns may arise if peer pressure or social norms reinforce stereotypical gender roles or if students face social consequences for deviating	Identify students who demonstrate strong communication skills, empathy, and impartiality to serve as peer mediators.	1 Day	Teacher and Students	100	Peer Observations

	from these norms.					
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DISCUSSION

Classroom management and student behavior in Grade 10 require a balanced approach to address the unique challenges of this developmental stage. At this level, students are transitioning into more mature roles while still navigating adolescence, which often brings heightened emotions, social pressures, and a quest for independence. Effective classroom management involves establishing clear rules and expectations, fostering mutual respect, and maintaining consistency in enforcing boundaries. Teachers must adopt proactive strategies, such as engaging lesson plans and interactive activities, to keep students motivated and focused. Building positive relationships is equally crucial; when students feel valued and understood, they are more likely to exhibit cooperative behavior. Additionally, addressing disruptive behavior promptly yet empathetically helps maintain a conducive learning environment. By combining structure, empathy, and engaging teaching methods, educators can guide Grade 10 students toward academic success and personal growth.

Conclusions

Most of the respondents were female, while the 17- and 18-year-old age brackets have the most and the least respondents, respectively. In terms of classroom management, learning style and classroom environment they had the highest (3.59) and the lowest (3.01) means, respectively. There is a statistical relationship between classroom management and students' behavior in terms of learning style. There is a statistical relationship between classroom management and students' behavior in terms of classroom environment. Respondents with demographic profiles of gender with significant differences in age, the levels of classroom management, and student behavior do not vary significantly among the groups based on the chosen characteristics. There is no significant difference between the demographic profile (i.e., age and gender) and the classroom management and students' behavior.

Recommendations

1. Students must cultivate self-discipline and take responsibility for their actions. This includes adhering to classroom rules, respecting teachers and peers, and managing their time effectively. Completing assignments punctually and preparing for classes are fundamental aspects of responsible behavior that contribute to a well-managed classroom.
2. Parents should communicate regularly with teachers to stay informed about their children's progress and behavior. Creating a supportive home environment that values education and good behavior is essential. Assisting with homework and

encouraging good study habits are practical ways to support their children's academic journey.

3. Teachers should design interactive and engaging lessons that cater to diverse learning styles. Active monitoring of student behavior and prompt addressing of issues are crucial for maintaining order and engagement. Continuous professional development helps teachers stay updated with effective classroom management strategies.
4. Future Researchers analyzing educational policies related to classroom management and their implementation can highlight best practices and areas for improvement. Disseminating successful case studies can guide schools in adopting effective management strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

It is important to protect the confidentiality and privacy of students taking part in research in order to promote candid and transparent involvement. This was accomplished by the use of multiple ethical procedures. All participating students were first given a thorough description of the study's objectives, the data collection procedure, and how their information would be used in order to acquire their informed permission. Additionally, students were given the assurance that they would not be penalized if they left the study at any point. The second step was to secure student identities during data analysis by replacing or removing any personally identifiable information, including names, school names, and contact information. To increase confidentiality, the usage of pseudonyms was also taken into consideration. Third, by limiting access to approved personnel, utilizing encryption when required, and storing the data safely, the researchers protected the information they had gathered.

Acknowledgments

This paper would not have been possible without the assistance, advice, and encouragement of the individuals to whom the researchers owe their gratitude. The researchers wish to express their heartfelt appreciation to the following individuals for their invaluable contributions to the study's success:

First and foremost, gratitude is extended to God, who blessed the researchers with wisdom, guidance, strength, and His blessings throughout the study.

The researchers express sincere gratitude to their thesis adviser, Ms. Emma Zalsos, PhD, for her continuous support, patience, motivation, enthusiasm, and immense knowledge. Her guidance was instrumental during the research and writing of this thesis, and her mentorship greatly contributed to the study's success.

Acknowledgment is also given to the Chairman and Dean of the College of Education, Dr. Juliet S. Timbang, as well as to the panel members, Ms. Rowena Jane P. Calo, MAEd, and Ms. Virginia N. Nadayag, MAEd, for their wise and kind suggestions that significantly improved the study.

The researchers also thank the respondents for their hospitality and cooperation in answering the questionnaires.

Appreciation is extended to the researchers' friends from both inside and outside the school, particularly those from their section, for their unwavering support and encouragement during moments of difficulty and confusion.

Gratitude is also expressed to the researchers' families, Hadji Amer, Nasroddin, and Zuasola, for their unconditional love, prayers, and financial and emotional support throughout the research process.

Finally, special thanks go to Ms. Emelyn L. Maambong and Mr. John Carl N. Mercado for their encouragement, motivation, and support in completing this study. Their ability to bring laughter and smiles during challenging times helped stabilize the researchers' emotions and mindset.

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